

Automatic Speech Bubble and Sound Effect Removal System for Webtoons Using AI Inpainting and Geometric Algorithms

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Abstract

Speech bubble and sound effect removal is an essential preprocessing task for the global distribution and re-editing of webtoon and comic content, yet existing approaches have heavily relied on manual labor. This paper proposes a system that combines geometric shape analysis-based algorithms with AI inpainting to automatically remove speech bubbles and sound effects from webtoon images. The proposed method precisely extracts speech bubble regions through FloodFill-based boundary detection, boundary point refinement, and shape classification, generating boundary point-based masks for natural background restoration via AI inpainting models. Experimental results demonstrate stable removal of speech bubbles and sound effects across diverse shapes and background conditions, with effective handling of complex cases involving overlapping structures and tails. This study presents a practical speech bubble removal system applicable not only to webtoon translation and editing automation but also to AI training data construction and content production efficiency enhancement.

1. Introduction

Webtoon and comic content are rapidly expanding through digital platforms, with increasing demand for automation technologies in translation, re-editing, and repurposing processes. Particularly in webtoon translation for global distribution, removing speech bubbles and sound effects from original images and re-inserting translated text is an essential requirement. However, current production workflows largely rely on manual speech bubble removal, which is time-consuming, costly, and prone to quality variations depending on worker expertise.

Existing automated approaches typically treat speech bubble regions as simple bounding boxes or perform inpainting across entire images, often damaging surrounding background areas outside the bubbles. Moreover, they fail to adequately account for webtoon-specific visual characteristics such as speech bubble shapes, outlines, background transparency, and tail structures, making natural removal results difficult to achieve. To address these challenges, this study proposes an automated system for accurately recognizing and removing speech bubbles and sound effects from webtoon images.

The proposed system precisely extracts speech bubble boundaries through geometric shape analysis, generates inpainting masks using boundary point information, and applies AI inpainting models to naturally restore speech bubble interior regions. The primary contribution of this study is presenting an integrated pipeline that combines algorithm-based detection—considering speech bubble shapes and structures—with AI inpainting, enabling fully automated removal of speech bubbles and sound effects from webtoons with practical applicability.

2. Related Work

In automated research for webtoon and comic translation, speech bubble detection and text recognition have been utilized as core preprocessing steps. Kim et al.[1] proposed a manga translation pipeline that detects speech bubble

regions using YOLOv8-based object detection and integrates OCR and translation modules. While this method enables stable speech bubble localization at the bounding box level, it does not separately address tail direction or detailed geometric shape analysis. Similarly, the Koharu project[5] implements a practical manga translation system including speech bubble detection, OCR, and inpainting; however, detection results are primarily processed at the bounding box level, limiting precise handling of shape analysis or overlapping situations. Consequently, existing studies have focused on localization for translation purposes, leaving room for more refined shape-based approaches to naturally remove speech bubbles and sound effects.

Research on text removal and restoration in images has primarily targeted general scene images, signs, or document images. Park et al.[2] proposed a GAN-based model that removes text from images while preserving surrounding background styles, performing natural restoration through generative models after masking text regions. Verduyn[3] analyzed GAN architectures for comic-style image generation and discussed how comic data characteristics and preprocessing methods impact result quality. Meanwhile, the commercial service Manga & Comic Text Cleaner[4] provides an inpainting-based tool for automatically removing text from manga and webtoon images, though its internal algorithms and mask generation methods remain undisclosed. While these existing inpainting studies and tools are effective for text removal itself, they leave unaddressed areas in precise mask generation that considers webtoon-specific speech bubble shapes, outlines, and background transparency.

Research actively exploring AI applications across webtoon production and editing processes is also underway. Kim et al.[5] analyzed how artificial intelligence technologies can be applied to various stages such as coloring, background generation, and editing assistance in webtoon production, while suggesting possibilities for post-production automation. Park et al.[6] proposed an on-device generative AI structure for webtoon content support, focusing on user interface improvement and editing efficiency. However, these studies remain at the level of editing assistance or production support, without addressing specific algorithmic methods for automatically recognizing and removing speech bubbles and sound effects. In contrast, this study proposes a system that automatically removes speech bubbles and sound effects from webtoon images by combining geometric shape analysis of speech bubbles with AI inpainting.

3. Proposed Method

3.1 Overall Pipeline

Figure 1. (A) Input: webtoon/comic image, (B) detection of speech bubble and sound effect regions, (C) AI-based inpainting, (D) output: image with speech bubbles and sound effects removed

The system proposed in this study combines a geometric shape analysis-based detection algorithm with an AI inpainting model to automatically remove speech bubbles and sound effects (SFX) from webtoon images. The

pipeline takes webtoon or comic images as input, extracts text bounding boxes through OCR, and performs FloodFill-based speech bubble boundary detection. Subsequently, boundary point refinement and shape analysis determine the speech bubble type and attributes, converting these boundary points into an inpainting mask. The generated mask and original image are fed into the AI inpainting model to naturally restore the speech bubble interior regions, ultimately outputting images with speech bubbles and SFX removed.

3.2 Speech Bubble and SFX Detection

Figure 2. Examples of Diverse Speech Bubbles Detected Using FloodFill

Speech bubble detection is performed based on text bounding boxes detected by OCR. The four corners outside the text bounding box are set as seed points, and the FloodFill algorithm is applied to fill areas similar to the background color, thereby isolating the speech bubble region. This process yields the speech bubble boundary mask, boundary point coordinate list, filled area size, and outer bounding box. The FloodFill process is designed to handle diverse background colors and luminance variations in webtoon images through color threshold and connectivity parameters. The same procedure can distinguish and detect SFX regions from speech bubbles.

3.3 Boundary Refinement and Shape Analysis

Figure 3. (A) FloodFill-based detection, (B) boundary point refinement, (C) speech bubble background analysis, (D) outline analysis, (E) overlap detection and coordinate transformation, (F) shape classification

Boundary points obtained from FloodFill may contain noise and duplicate points, necessitating a boundary refinement process. First, points within the text bounding box and exclusion areas are removed, the center point of remaining boundary points is calculated, and points are sorted by angle. Distance-based duplicate removal techniques are then applied to merge points within a certain distance, smoothing the boundary line. Based on the refined boundary points, geometric features such as circularity, convexity, aspect ratio, and fill ratio are calculated, and curvature-based corner detection analyzes speech bubble shapes. These feature values are comprehensively evaluated to classify speech bubble shapes—such as rectangular, oval, pointed, and oval-with-tail—using a score-based approach.

3.4 Mask Generation from Edge Points

Refined boundary point coordinates are converted into mask images for inpainting. A canvas of the same size as the original image is created, with non-inpainting areas initialized to black. Boundary point coordinates are sequentially connected to form a polygonal path, and the interior of this polygon is filled as the inpainting target area. This study uses a single yellow-toned color for the inpainting region to clearly delineate it, and the final mask image is converted to Base64 PNG format for input to the inpainting model.

3.5 AI-based Inpainting

The mask image and original image are input to a proprietary AI inpainting model to restore speech bubble and SFX regions. The proposed inpainting model is designed to stably handle relatively large missing areas, learning surrounding background patterns and textures to generate natural results even after speech bubble interiors are

removed. It specifically considers webtoon-specific features such as flat color areas, gradient backgrounds, and repeating patterns to maintain visual consistency with surrounding speech bubble backgrounds.

3. 6 Output Integration

The inpainted result image is merged with the original image to produce the final output. The original image serves as the base canvas, and inpainting results are composited by overwriting corresponding positions, preserving original information outside speech bubble areas during this process. The final result image is converted to JPEG Base64 data format for system output and can be utilized for subsequent translation text insertion or additional editing tasks.

4. Evaluation Method

To evaluate the performance of the proposed system, qualitative evaluation-focused experiments were conducted using webtoon and comic image datasets. The experimental data consisted of webtoon panel images containing various speech bubble shapes and sound effects (SFX), selected to reflect real-world webtoon environments including solid color backgrounds, gradient backgrounds, and complex pattern backgrounds. The evaluation aims to verify whether speech bubbles and SFX are accurately removed and whether the background is naturally restored after removal.

Quantitative image quality metrics were applied only limitedly due to the inherent nature of speech bubble removal tasks, where identical ground-truth reference images do not exist. Instead, evaluation centered on visual quality and processing stability. The evaluation criteria comprised: (1) speech bubble and SFX removal accuracy, (2) background restoration naturalness, (3) preservation of speech bubble outlines and surrounding objects, and (4) successful handling of overlapping and tail structures. Each criterion was repeatedly verified across diverse speech bubble types, analyzing removal failures, residual artifacts, and background distortions.

Additionally, visual comparisons of results from applying the proposed method to identical images confirmed that speech bubble interior regions were consistently restored to match surrounding backgrounds. Through these evaluation methods, this study verifies the effectiveness of the proposed algorithm and AI inpainting combination for automatically removing speech bubbles and SFX from webtoon images.

5. Experimental Results

Figure 4. Examples of Speech Bubble and Sound Effect Detection with AI-based Inpainting

This study evaluated the automatic speech bubble and sound effect (SFX) removal performance by applying the proposed system to various webtoon images. The experimental results confirmed that the proposed method can stably detect and remove speech bubble regions across diverse shapes, including rectangular, oval, pointed, and tail-included speech bubbles. Particularly, boundary point-based shape analysis enabled precise extraction of speech bubble outlines, effectively reducing excessive removal area issues that occurred with simple bounding box approaches.

In AI inpainting results, speech bubble interior regions were naturally restored by reflecting surrounding

background colors and patterns, minimizing visual discontinuities even with gradient backgrounds and repeating patterns beyond solid color backgrounds. For overlapping speech bubbles or complex structures with tails, coordinate transformation-based analysis accurately estimated tail directions and separated speech bubble regions, improving removal success rates. Minor residual traces were observed in cases of extremely complex backgrounds or when speech bubble outlines had colors similar to the background; however, these did not significantly impact overall removal quality.

Visual comparison results demonstrated that the proposed method well preserves surrounding objects and background forms even after speech bubble removal, providing results suitable for subsequent translation text insertion or additional editing tasks. These experimental findings demonstrate that the proposed system possesses practical performance for automatically removing speech bubbles and SFX from webtoon images.

6. Conclusion

This study proposes a system that combines geometric shape analysis-based detection algorithms with AI inpainting to automatically remove speech bubbles and sound effects from webtoon images. The proposed method extracts precise speech bubble regions through FloodFill-based boundary detection, boundary point refinement, and shape classification, converting them into inpainting masks to perform natural background restoration. Experimental results demonstrated stable removal performance across various speech bubble shapes and background conditions, effectively handling complex cases involving overlapping structures and tails.

The proposed system significantly reduces manual labor in webtoon translation and re-editing processes and can be utilized for AI training data construction requiring speech bubble removal and content editing automation. Future research will expand the system's applicability by improving generalization performance across diverse webtoon styles, developing quantitative metrics for inpainting quality evaluation, and enhancing real-time processing capabilities.

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